

**Degradation of organic pollutants combining plasma
discharges generated within soil with TiO₂ and ZnO
catalysts: Comparative analysis, optimization and
mechanisms**

by

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Abstract

An advantageous cold atmospheric plasma setup in which micro-discharges are generated directly into the interconnected soil channels was combined for the first time with TiO₂ and ZnO catalysts towards the degradation of trifluralin. In the presence of these catalysts, a significant increase of the degradation efficiency and rate was observed for both TiO₂ and ZnO, with TiO₂ being a slightly superior catalyst compared to ZnO. The dominance of reactive oxygen species (ROS) over reactive nitrogen species (RNS) was determined by using different plasma gases whereas the inhibitory effect of soil humidity in the degradation process was also confirmed, although less pronounced in the presence of catalysts. The detection of plasma species in the gas phase and the exhaust gases revealed that the presence of TiO₂ and ZnO resulted in a significant increase in NO₂ concentration and a noticeable reduction in O₃ generation compared to the plasma alone process associated with an increase of certain plasma species concentration and the generation of additional and more active ROS, respectively. Liquid chromatography (UPLC/MS) data at the early stages of the degradation process in the presence and absence of the photocatalysts provided insight into the mechanisms and intermediates involved in the degradation of trifluralin in soil under plasma co-operative catalysis. Finally, the significance of the method in the context of energy efficiency was exemplified. Inclusion of a catalyst in our system resulted in a ~3fold increase in energy efficiency. The present effort supports the potential of future implementation of a plasmacatalytic-based soil remediation method being a rapid, highly efficient, low energy demanding and green method.

Keywords: Plasmacatalysis; Dielectric barrier discharge; Cold plasma; Photocatalysts; Trifluralin degradation; Soil remediation.

1. Introduction

Soil has long been proposed as the “most complex biomaterial on the planet”. This is a reasonable claim considering that it acts as a habitat for living organisms, a hydrological regulator of water quality and quantity and a nutrient source tank. As a consequence of human activities, a myriad of organic pollutants including pesticides, pharmaceuticals, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and flame retardants ends up in soil [1].

Cold atmospheric plasma (CAP) has been widely implemented for water purification being an innovative, green and highly efficient method for the removal of organic pollutants; its superior performance being based on the high oxidation potential of the plasma-generated reactive oxygen and nitrogen species (RONS), such as hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$), singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$), atomic oxygen ($\cdot\text{O}$), ozone (O_3) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) [2]. During the last decade, more and more CAP efforts have been applied for the remediation of polluted soil [2-5]. Among the various CAP systems, dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) and pulsed corona discharge (PCD) are the most frequently found effective against different types of contaminants including diesel fuel [6], non-aqueous phase liquids (NAPLs) [4, 5], polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) [7, 8], pesticides [9, 10], antibiotics and perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) [11]. In all these studies, plasma species were generated above the contaminated medium and afterwards diffused inside soil. Recently, the generation of plasma discharges directly inside the network of pores of the contaminated soil revealed enhanced process energy efficiency due to the enhancement of the mass transport and interaction of plasma species with the pollutant molecules [12-14]. Furthermore, when high voltage nanosecond pulses (NSP) are used for the generation of the plasma species, an extremely high energy efficiency of the degradation process is achieved [14, 15].

Given that plasmacatalysis is an emerging field with promising results in the field of wastewater treatment [2, 16-18], a step forward in soil remediation could be the combination of the most energy efficient CAP reactor (RONS generation directly inside soil pores driven by HV nanopulses) with catalysts. In this way, higher pollutant degradation efficiency can be achieved using the optimum reactor, while the use of catalysts is expected to improve degradation rate and the CAP performance overall, resulting in lower energy requirements. To the best of our knowledge, studies combining CAP with catalysts for soil remediation are scarce whereas plasmacatalytic mechanisms remain unexplored. In particular, the combination of a pulsed discharge plasma system with Al₂O₃-supported metal oxide catalysts enhanced the removal efficiency of PAHs from soil up to 20-40% although this required high catalyst loading (23 w/w%) [19]. In another report, ~20% higher degradation efficiency was achieved for the removal p-nitrophenol when 2 w/w% TiO₂ was combined with plasma [20]. Recently, the addition of CeO₂ and TiO₂ catalysts in a DBD system significantly improved the degradation efficiency of pyrene by 15-16%, highlighting the obvious synergistic effect with plasma [21]. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO) are two of the most widely used photo-catalysts due to their low-cost, high surface area, robustness, abundance and non-toxicity [22-26].

To date, there are no studies on plasma-catalytic soil remediation comparing the performance of TiO₂ and ZnO. Hence, in this work, TiO₂ and ZnO catalysts were combined for the first time with plasma discharges generated directly inside the interconnected pore channels of the soil towards the degradation of trifluralin (a typical agrochemical/organic soil contaminant) and the plasma-catalytic synergies were thoroughly studied (which remain almost unexplored). Trifluralin is one of the most commonly used herbicides and classified by the World Health Organization (W.H.O)

as neurotoxic, embryotoxic, carcinogenic and extremely toxic to aquatic organisms. Due to its hydrophobic nature, trifluralin has the potential to persist in soil for years depending on site-specific agro-climatic conditions [27]. Several experimental conditions in the presence/absence of catalysts were investigated, such as treatment time, catalyst loading, plasma gas and soil moisture. A detailed catalysts' characterization was also performed, whereas the excited short-lived plasma species with and without catalysts in the gas phase along with the plasma-induced long-lived NO₂ and O₃ concentration in the reactor's exhaust gases were also determined. Furthermore, several plasma-induced oxidation intermediates of trifluralin (with and without catalysts) were identified. These data provided insight into the different mechanisms and intermediates involved in the early stages of the degradation of trifluralin in soil in the presence and absence of catalysts.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials and reagents

Trifluralin (PESTANAL, analytical standard) and clean sandy soil were both provided by Sigma Aldrich and were used as model pollutant and soil, respectively. Soil porosity and moisture content were determined to be 0.49 and 0.1%, respectively. The grain size distribution was in the range of 100-420 µm and its pH was equal to 7.5 when wet. The catalysts TiO₂ (Titanium (IV) oxide nanopowder, 21 nm particle size P25, Sigma Aldrich), and ZnO (Zinc oxide nanopowder, <100 nm particle size, Sigma Aldrich) were used without any pretreatment in the plasmacatalytic experiments. Methanol was of analytical grade (purchased from Sigma Aldrich) and used without further purification.

2.2. Catalysts morphology characterization before and after plasma

X-ray powder diffraction (pXRD) analysis took place employing a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2 θ angle range 20 to 85 degrees. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) imaging was performed on a JEM2100 JEOL at 200 kV. SPECS Phoibos 100- 1D-DLD was employed for the X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) under ultrahigh vacuum at room temperature using non-monochromatized Mg K α radiation (20 eV analyzer pass energy). For TiO₂ samples charge correction took place for the spectra of all elements by fixing the binding energy of C 1s at 284.6 eV. Mixed Gaussian-Lorentzian peaks with Shirley background were used for the analysis of the spectra.

2.3. Experimental setup, treatment conditions and electrical discharge properties

The schematic representation of the experimental setup used to treat contaminated soil samples and characterize the plasma is presented in Fig.1a. The system is comprised by a dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) reactor of coaxial geometry, a nanosecond pulsed (NSP) high voltage (HV) power supply, a gas supplying system, compartments for the electrical and optical characterization of the discharge, gas analyzers for the measurement of the plasma gaseous molecules (O₃ and NO_x) in the reactor exhaust gases and equipment for the chemical analysis of the plasma-treated soil samples.

The coaxial DBD reactor is presented in detail in our previous studies [13, 14]. Briefly, the reactor consisted of a stainless-steel cylindrical HV electrode, a quartz dielectric tube and a stainless-steel grid attached to the exterior surface of the dielectric tube serving as the grounded electrode of the discharge. The soil was loaded and entirely filled the space between the HV electrode and the dielectric ensuring that micro-discharges were directly generated around the surface of the interconnected soil grains. Therefore, the novelty of this reactor lies on the production of micro-discharges within

the contaminated soil allowing at the same time the simulation in the lab of an in-situ soil remediation by plasma (in-soil approach). Considering that this reactor configuration exhibited superior performance compared to plasma reactors where the plasma is produced above the soil surface, this is the first attempt where this in-soil plasma system is investigated in conjunction with catalyst for soil remediation (Fig. 1b). The mass of the treated soil was 10.1 g, the HV electrode diameter was 1.8 mm, the electrode gap was 6.0 mm, the dielectric thickness was 1.7 mm whereas the soil thickness and length were 4.3 mm and 2.5 cm, respectively. Based on previous findings [14], the experiments were performed at constant flow rate (0.075 L min^{-1}) of various plasma working gases (air, oxygen and nitrogen) controlled by an Aalborg GFC17 mass flow controller.

The HV generator (NPG-18/3500) was able to produce positive nanosecond pulses ($\sim 4 \text{ ns}$). The pulse voltage was set equal to 22.2 kV and the pulse repetition rate was kept at 100 Hz. A digital oscilloscope (Rigol MSO2302A, 300 MHz, 2 GSamples/s) was used for the electrical measurements by monitoring the waveforms of the current and the voltage nanopulses by means of a wideband current transformer (Pearson electronics 2877, 300 Hz-200 MHz) and a voltage probe (Tektronix P6015A, 0-75 MHz), respectively. The power (P) dissipated in the reactor was determined by the following equation:

$$P = f E_p = f \int_{pulse} V(t)I(t)dt \quad (1)$$

where f is the pulse repetition rate, while $V(t)$ and $I(t)$ are the measured voltage and current waveforms, respectively. The instantaneous voltage, current and power waveforms are presented in Fig. 1c. The maximum pulse current was $\sim 60 \text{ A}$ which is $\sim 2\text{-}3$ orders of magnitude higher of the corresponding one measured in sinusoidal-driven DBD reactors (AC-DBDs) [10] leading to an enormously high instantaneous

power ~ 1.3 MW (Fig. 1c). The very high instantaneous power along with the quite low mean DBD power (calculated equal to 0.47 W) is the key of the extremely high energy efficiency of the nanosecond pulsed (NSP) systems [28].

2.4. Detection of plasma species and measurement of temperature

Optical emission spectroscopy measurements were conducted for the identification of the main excited plasma species in the gas phase (Fig. 1d). Emission spectra of the plasma discharge in the range of 200–900 nm were recorded by means of a fiber optics spectrometer (AvaSpec-ULS2048CL-EVO, Avantes). The concentration of the plasma-generated NO_x and O_3 in the exhaust gases were recorded using a gas (Optima 7) and an ozone analyzer (Ozone Analyzer BMT 965, MESSTECHNIK), respectively. All aforementioned measurements were conducted in non-polluted soil in the presence and in the absence of catalysts; this could provide an important indication of the impact of the catalysts in the plasma process.

A thermocouple attached to the ground electrode was used to measure the temperature via a digital multimeter (Mastech MS8209). The initial temperature was ~ 20 °C and increased slightly to ~ 22 °C at the end of the treatment (i.e. 10 min).

Figure 1. (a) Schematic representation of the setup used to treat trifluralin-contaminated soil and characterize the plasma, (b) the main features of the soil treatment approaches followed in this study, (c) instantaneous voltage, current and power waveforms of the NSP-driven coaxial DBD reactor and (d) principal excited plasma species during air-plasma in the absence and in the presence of TiO₂ and ZnO (catalyst loading: 2 wt%).

2.5. Preparation of contaminated soil, extraction and chemical analysis

The procedure followed for the contamination of soil samples included the dissolution of the pollutant in methanol under stirring and the subsequent immersion of the soil into the pollutant's solution. Afterwards, methanol was evaporated in a rotary evaporator at 50 °C, resulting in a homogeneously polluted soil with the initial concentration of trifluralin being 200 mg/kg-soil. Appropriate amounts of powdered TiO₂ and ZnO were fully mixed with the soil before the plasmacatalytic experiments resulting in various catalyst loadings in soil (i.e. 0.5, 1 and 2 wt%).

The recovery of organic compounds from soil samples was achieved using methanol as the extraction solvent. The extraction method is fully described in our previous work [13]. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC, Agilent 1100) coupled with a UV-Vis detector was used to quantify the residual concentration of trifluralin in soil. In order to identify relevant intermediates and compare their abundancies in the TiO₂ and ZnO plasma-catalytic processes against those manifested in the plasma alone conditions, samples taken after 1 min of treatment in each case were analyzed by UPLC/MS (details can be found in S1). The structure of the intermediates detected are proposed based on their molecular ions in positive and negative ionizations modes, fragmentation patterns and elution time (polarity) in the UPLC reverse phase column. The determination of the pollutant degradation efficiency, $D(\%)$, was based on the following equation:

$$D(\%) = \left[\frac{C_0 - C_f}{C_0} \right] \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where C_0 and C_f are the trifluralin's concentration before and after CAP treatment, respectively.

In order to evaluate the degradation rate, a pseudo-first order reaction with respect to the pollutant concentration was assumed and the degradation kinetics were fitted using the following equation:

$$\ln\left(\frac{C_0}{C_f}\right) = kt \quad (3)$$

where k is the apparent rate constant.

The calculation of the energy efficiency (E ; mg/kJ) was done by the following equation:

$$E = \frac{m_{triflu}}{P \times t} \quad (4)$$

where m_{triflu} is the mass of the degraded trifluralin, t is the treatment time and P is the power of the DBD. All experiments were performed at least in duplicate exhibiting high reproducibility.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. The impact of plasma treatment on the catalysts' morphology

The catalysts were characterized prior to use with respect to their structure and morphology. Fig. S1 shows representative TEM images of the TiO₂ and ZnO samples used in this study, while the obtained XRD spectra are presented in Fig. S2. The almost spherical TiO₂ nanoparticles have a mean diameter close to 20 nm (Fig. S1), while the dominant phase (~90%) is anatase (Fig. S2). ZnO particles have a hexagonal wurtzite structure with a mean size <100 nm, within specifications. The surface area of ZnO is thus lower compared to that of TiO₂. Details regarding XRD analysis can be found in S2.

It is well reported that catalysts affect the plasma properties and vice versa. XPS measurements also took place in order to study the surface chemical composition of the nanoparticles, as well as the oxidation states of the elements. In addition, the as-

received samples were treated under air-CAP for 2 and 10 min to detect possible changes in the structure. Starting with the TiO₂ samples, upon the air-CAP treatment, the atom ratio O/Ti increased only slightly from 2.5 to 2.7 (Table S2a). Fig. 2a shows the Ti 2p XPS spectra of the different TiO₂ samples, where the standard Ti 2p_{3/2} and Ti 2p_{1/2} peaks can be seen. Ti⁴⁺ is the main valence state presenting a binding energy (BE) of the stronger Ti 2p_{3/2} at 458.5 eV (full width at half maximum FWHM=1.4 eV) and a spin orbit splitting of 5.72 eV, according to literature [29, 30]. The FWHM of Ti 2p_{3/2} was about 1.4 eV, as determined from the fitting. The 3⁺ charge state would appear at about 1.8 eV lower than Ti⁴⁺ and the analysis of the spectra did not present such a component in any of the samples. As is evident from the figure, in the pristine sample, as well as after the CAP treatment, there is no observed peak shifting or any shoulder that could denote the presence of Ti³⁺ or any other oxides with intermediate Ti state. In this respect, CAP treatment followed in this work provoked no changes in the state of Ti element, unlike thermal plasma that has been reported to induce notable Ti-O bonds scission and oxygen deficiencies [31] evidenced also by a structural change and corresponding increase in the percentage of Ti³⁺ species.

Nevertheless, a small oxygen deficiency within the matrix is still possible thus, the oxygen core level spectra were measured and analyzed. Fig. 2b shows the XPS O 1s spectra of the TiO₂ samples. A distinct increase of the peak's shoulder in the 531-533 eV region can be detected. Following this observation, all O 1s spectra were deconvoluted as presented in the inset of the figure and the results are presented in Table S2a. More specifically, the main O 1s peak is positioned at BE 529.8 eV and is attributed to the O-Ti lattice bond in TiO₂ [32]. The peak at 531.0 eV corresponds to a component related to oxygen vacancies [33] and seems to be slightly affected by the CAP treatment, while a serious increase in the peak at 533.3-533.5 eV is observed with

increasing the air-CAP treatment time [34]. The latter peak (low binding energy component, LBEC) is commonly attributed to non-lattice oxygen which is associated with adsorption of the hydroxyl groups (Ti-OH) on the surface of amorphous TiO₂ [35]. Despite Ti and oxygen, a very small amount of nitrogen was also evidenced by XPS, in the pristine as well as the treated samples, that remained unaffected and positioned at about 400.3 eV (atom ratio N/Ti ~ 0.04), often in literature attributed to Ti-O-N species [36].

Fig. 2c shows the XPS Zn 2p spectra of pristine ZnO, before and after air-CAP treatment. The characteristic Zn 2p doublet peaks appear, corresponding to 2p_{3/2} and 2p_{1/2} having 23 eV difference between the two bonding energies, as is well reported for the 2⁺ oxidation state of Zn [37-39]. The Zn 2p_{3/2} component is positioned at 1022.32-1022.37 eV [40] and the spectrum of the initial ZnO sample seems unaffected by the CAP treatment. According to the XPS spectra collected, the atom O/Zn ratio increased by 45-48% after CAP. The corresponding XPS O 1s spectra are presented in Fig. 2d. Their direct comparison shows a change in the 532-534 eV region. The asymmetric peaks indicate the co-existence of different species thus the spectra were deconvoluted using three single components [41] O1 to O3 (FWHM about 1.44), Fig. 2d (inset) and Table S2b. The first peak O1 at about 531 eV is attributed to the oxygen atoms in a fully oxidized stoichiometric surrounding, in the Zn-O bonding of the ZnO wurtzite structure [40], while O2 peak is related to the oxygen deficiency or vacancies [38, 42]. The final O3 peak at the highest BE is associated to weaker bonds of oxygen like OH group absorbed onto the surface [37]. The increased O/Zn ratio is accompanied by decreased percentage of the O2 and O3 oxygen components (Table S2b), which is in accordance with previous studies which showed that plasma treatment led to reduced oxygen vacancies and improved crystallinity [43, 44]. In conclusion, the air-CAP

treatment followed in this work only enriched the surface of TiO₂ with non-lattice oxygen, whereas in the case of ZnO it affected the structure by seriously increasing the surface oxygen (increased O/Zn ratio). In the latter case, both the lattice oxygen (O1) and the vacancies (O2) increased after CAP, while their relative ratio (O2/O1) decreased.

Figure 2. XPS (a) Ti 2p, (b) O 1s spectra of TiO₂ as received and after 2 and 10 min of air-plasma treatment, (c) Zn 2p, (d) O 1s spectra of ZnO as received and after 2 and 10 min of air-plasma treatment. Insets in (b and d) show an example (for the sample after 10 min of plasma treatment) of the deconvolution of the oxygen spectra into single components.

3.2. Effect of catalyst loading on degradation efficiency, rate and energy efficiency

In order to determine the effect of both TiO₂ and ZnO catalysts on the trifluralin degradation efficiency, three different catalyst loadings in soil were investigated (Fig. 3). Each catalyst was homogeneously mixed with soil at 0.5, 1 and 2 wt% loadings. The effect of different TiO₂ loadings on pollutant degradation is presented in Fig. 3a. Obviously, the presence of TiO₂ increased the degradation performance substantially in agreement with previously reported results on p-nitrophenol and pyrene degradation in soil by TiO₂-plasmacatalysis [20, 21]. In particular, the increase of TiO₂ loading up to 1% increased the trifluralin degradation efficiency significantly, especially at short treatment times, whereas even higher TiO₂ loading (2 wt%) had a positive impact only on the pollutant degradation rate. For instance, after 2 min of air-CAP treatment, degradation efficiency was 30.9% for plasma alone process, while it was increased to 44.8, 70.0 and 82.2% with the addition of 0.5, 1 and 2 wt% TiO₂ (air-CAP/TiO₂), respectively. This positive TiO₂-effect was also reflected at higher treatment times; after 5 min-CAP the degradation efficiency increased from ~66.5% (air-CAP alone) to ~94.2% at 2 wt% TiO₂ loading in soil. It is also noticeable that at the end of CAP treatment (10 min), the degradation of trifluralin in soil was almost complete (>99.5%) in the presence of 1-2 wt% TiO₂ in contrast to air-CAP alone where trifluralin was degraded ~90% (Fig. 3a). The addition of ZnO catalyst to the soil also led to enhanced degradation of trifluralin (Fig. 3b). Indicatively, at short treatment times (i.e. 3 min), degradation efficiency was 47.5% for air-CAP alone, whereas it was increased at 59.6, 74.2 and 89% with the addition of 0.5, 1 and 2 wt% ZnO, respectively. Similar to the TiO₂ effect, at longer plasma treatment times, complete trifluralin's degradation was achieved (~99.9%) after 10 min of air-CAP/ZnO.

The corresponding pseudo-first-order kinetics of trifluralin degradation at different catalyst loadings for both TiO₂ and ZnO are shown in Fig. 3c. For both catalysts, the apparent rate constant k was an increasing function of catalyst loading. In particular, k was increased from 0.23 min⁻¹ (air-CAP alone) to 0.37, 0.54 and 0.68 min⁻¹ at 0.5, 1 and 2 wt% TiO₂, respectively. Similarly, k was increased to 0.29, 0.36 and 0.67 min⁻¹ at 0.5, 1 and 2 wt% ZnO, respectively. It is noteworthy that a relatively higher catalytic activity was observed for TiO₂ at 0.5-1 wt% loading range, whereas at 2 wt% catalyst loading both catalysts performed equally (Fig. 3c). This may be rationalized by the vital role of plasma species in the degradation process and their relative concentration which in turn depends on the type and loading of a catalyst (see results in section 3.5). Because of the enhanced pollutant degradation, plasma-catalysis has been indicated as a valuable tool for enhancing process energy efficiency [2, 45]. Various approaches have been adopted to increase the energy efficiency of CAP process including the use of HV nanosecond pulses (NSP) instead of sinusoidal high voltage and/or the generation of plasma discharges directly inside the soil pores in contrast to plasma creation above the contaminated medium [13, 14]. In this study, the combination of NSP with in-soil generated plasma and catalysts is expected to further enhance the process energy efficiency. Thus, we calculated the energy efficiency (mg/kJ) of trifluralin's degradation in the present NSP-driven in-soil reactor in the presence and absence of TiO₂ and ZnO and the results are shown in Fig. 3d. Obviously, the presence of TiO₂ and ZnO significantly improved the energy efficiency of the present system. It is worth noting that for ~90% trifluralin degradation efficiency, the calculated energy efficiency increased from 6.5 mg/kJ (air-CAP) to 21.6 mg/kJ (air-CAP/TiO₂) and 21.2 mg/kJ (air-CAP/ZnO) (Fig. 6d); that is a 330% improvement. After 5 and 10 min of treatment, where pollutant degradation was almost complete in the presence of TiO₂

and ZnO catalysts (~94 and >99.9%, respectively), the corresponding energy efficiencies were extremely high and equal to 13.5 mg/kJ and 7.2 mg/kJ.

Figure 3. Effect of (a) TiO₂ and (b) ZnO loading on trifluralin's degradation efficiency, (plasma gas: air) (c) the pseudo-first-order apparent rate constants at different catalyst loading for both TiO₂ and ZnO and (d) the calculated energy efficiency (mg/kJ) of trifluralin's degradation in the presence and absence of TiO₂ and ZnO (catalyst loading: 2 wt%).

Various cold plasma systems, including dielectric barrier discharge (DBD), pulsed corona and gliding arc, have been proposed for the degradation of organic pollutants in soil. Obviously, the energy efficiency of the current in-soil plasma-catalytic system driven by NSP is about 2-3 orders of magnitude higher compared to plasma systems driven by other HV power sources (e.g. AC, microsecond pulses) where plasma is produced above the soil surface (Table 1). The energy efficiency enhancement due to NSP is related to the extremely high nanosecond instantaneous power (~ 1.3 MW, see Fig. 1c) in parallel to the very low mean power dissipated in the DBD (0.47 W in the present study). The formation of micro-discharges directly inside the soil matrix as opposed to plasma generation above the soil surface, has been found to increase further the energy efficiency due to the enhanced penetration and mass-transfer of RONS within soil pores and their interaction with pollutant molecules [13, 14]. Nevertheless, the addition of catalysts in our system increased further the energy efficiency (~ 3 fold) at a given value of pollutant degradation (Table 1, Fig 3d). Complete pollutant degradation along with improved degradation kinetics and enormously high energy efficiency, suggests that the present NSP-driven in-soil plasma-catalytic reactor can be considered as the most energy efficient plasma system to date in the literature. Nevertheless, a drawback of plasma-catalysis is that it causes secondary pollution. For this reason, immobilization of the catalysts should be explored, while the possibility of their easy separation from the soil at the end of the process could be considered through the use of catalysts that exhibit magnetic separation capability. The plasma-catalytic mechanisms leading to enhanced pollutant degradation and energy efficiency in the presence of TiO_2 and ZnO are discussed in detail below.

Table 1. Degradation and energy efficiency of various plasma methods either in the presence or absence of catalysts for soil remediation.

CAP method	Catalyst/ Loading	Soil/ Pollutant	Degradation efficiency/ Treatment time	Energy efficiency (mg/kJ)	Ref
NSP-DBD In-soil	-	Model sandy soil/Trifluralin (200 ppm)	90.3% (10 min)	6.5	This study
NSP-DBD In-soil	TiO ₂ /2 wt%	Model sandy soil/Trifluralin (200 ppm)	>90.4% (3 min) (i) >99.9% (10 min) (ii)	21.6 (i) 7.2 (ii)	This study
NSP-DBD In-soil	ZnO/2 wt%	Model sandy soil/Trifluralin (200 ppm)	>89% (3 min) (i) >99.9% (10 min) (ii)	21.2 (i) 7.2 (ii)	This study
AC-DBD Ex-situ soil	-	Loamy soil/Pyrene (105 ppm)	79.7% (30min)	0.0082	[8]
AC-DBD Ex-situ soil	-	Model sandy soil/Atrazine (200 ppm)	84.6% (60 min)	0.3	[10]
Pulsed Corona Ex-situ	-	Natural soil/PFOA (30 ppm)	71% (120min)	0.0039	[11]
Pulsed Corona Ex-situ	-	Natural soil/Phenanthrene (50 ppm)	74% (40min)	0.1	[46]
Pulsed Corona Ex-situ	No catalyst TiO ₂ /2 wt%	Natural soil/p-nitrophenol (800ppm)	78.1% 88.8%	-	[20]
AC-DBD	No catalyst MOFs/0.1 wt%	Model sandy soil/Fluorene (100 ppm)	71.4% (10min) 96.5% (10min)	-	[47]
AC-DBD Parallel tubes	No catalyst TiO ₂ /CeO ₂ /-	Simulated soil/Pyrene (100ppm)	25.5% (1 min) 66.2%/55.0% (1 min)	0.22 0.54/0.47	[21]

3.3. Effect of plasma gas in degradation efficiency

Plasma carrier gas controls the concentration and type of plasma-generated species thus strongly affecting the pollutant remediation efficiency [2, 48]. In order to investigate the role of different RONS in trifluralin degradation in the absence and presence of catalysts, plasma and plasma-catalytic experiments were repeated under air, oxygen and nitrogen atmospheres. In the absence of catalysts, the results are shown in Fig. 4a. After 10 min of CAP treatment, degradation efficiency reached 90.3%, 91.7% and 23.9%, under air, O₂ and N₂ gases, respectively. Trifluralin degradation fitted a pseudo-first-order kinetic model (Fig. S3) with the apparent rate constant k being 0.23 (air-CAP), 0.24 (O₂-CAP) and 0.04 min⁻¹ (N₂-CAP) (Fig. 4c). The similar degradation efficiency and rate under oxygen and air is in agreement with previous study on gasoline degradation in soil by pulsed corona [49]. The dominance of O₂-CAP and air-CAP towards trifluralin degradation could be attributed to the predominant role of plasma-generated ROS in comparison to RNS, given that an increased production of ROS is expected under oxygen-containing atmospheres compared to N₂ atmosphere. During O₂-CAP and air-CAP, electrons and various ROS (e.g. atomic oxygen, ozone, hydroxyl radicals) are generated through the reactions (5)-(7) contributing to the degradation of trifluralin:

Since the O₂ content under O₂-CAP is higher compared to air-CAP and leads to higher ROS concentrations (e.g. O₃, see results below in section 3.5, Fig. 6), an increased degradation efficiency was expected under O₂-CAP. The essentially identical and significant pollutant degradation in both cases indicates that even in the case of air-

CAP, high ROS concentrations are provided reaching the limit where further increase does not seriously affect the reaction rate for the same low pollutant concentration. However, it is also possible that NO_x generated from N₂ in the air (reactions 8-10) may contribute in the degradation process thus compensating for the reduction of ROS concentration in air-CAP compared to O₂-CAP.

In addition, the limited trifluralin degradation under nitrogen gas indicates a limited role of the electrons and other RNS (reactions 11-12), generated during N₂-CAP in the degradation process.

The comparison between O₂ and air plasma in the presence of TiO₂ and ZnO (1 wt%) is presented in Fig. 4b. It is observed for both catalysts that a higher degradation rate is achieved with O₂ compared to air regardless of treatment time, indicative of increased ROS concentration when O₂ is used as the carrier gas. This is in contrast with the catalyst-free O₂- and air-CAP processes which afforded essentially the same degradation efficiency, thus indicating a higher contribution or additional role of O₂ in the degradation process when appropriate catalysts are present. For example, after a 2 min treatment, degradation efficiency of trifluralin for 1% wt TiO₂ was 78.3% and 70% when O₂ and air were used, respectively, while the corresponding values for 1% wt ZnO were 76.6% and 61.5%. Nevertheless, at the end of the CAP treatment (i.e. 10 min), trifluralin was almost completely degraded under both O₂ and air in the presence of catalysts. In particular, the degradation efficiency was equal to 99.9% (O₂-CAP/TiO₂),

99.5% ($\text{O}_2\text{-CAP}/\text{ZnO}$), 99.4% ($\text{air-CAP}/\text{TiO}_2$) and 96% ($\text{air-CAP}/\text{ZnO}$). All data fitted a pseudo-first-order kinetic model (Fig. S4) with the apparent rate constant k being 0.72 ($\text{O}_2\text{-CAP}/\text{TiO}_2$) > 0.56 ($\text{O}_2\text{-CAP}/\text{ZnO}$) > 0.54 ($\text{air-CAP}/\text{TiO}_2$) and 0.36 min^{-1} ($\text{air-CAP}/\text{ZnO}$) (Fig. 4c). The higher pollutant degradation efficiency and rate achieved in the $\text{O}_2\text{-CAP}/\text{catalyst}$ system might be due to the higher degree of O_3 decomposition, in the presence of catalysts, to other ROS under $\text{O}_2\text{-CAP}$ compared to air-CAP (see discussion in section 3.5).

Figure 4. (a) Trifluralin's degradation efficiency under air, oxygen and nitrogen atmosphere for plasma-alone process; (b) effect of TiO_2 and ZnO on trifluralin's degradation efficiency under air and oxygen plasma; (c) apparent rate constants under the various gases in the presence and absence of catalysts (catalyst loading: 1 wt%).

3.4. Effect of soil humidity on degradation efficiency in the absence and presence of catalysts

Another generally critical parameter proved to affect the degradation efficiency is the soil humidity. In the present study, we examined the effect of soil moisture in the absence and presence of TiO₂ and ZnO during air-plasma. In Fig. 5, the degradation efficiency is presented as a function of soil moisture. Obviously, the existence of water in soil seemed to decrease significantly the degradation efficiency of trifluralin during the air-CAP alone process. After a 10 min treatment, the removal of trifluralin in low moisture soil (~0.2 wt%) was 90.3%, whereas when soil moisture was 2 and 5 wt% it was reduced to 52.3 and 41.4%, respectively corresponding to a reduction of ~42% and ~54%. It has been already reported that the presence of soil moisture hinders the transport of plasma RONS in the soil bulk and their penetration in water prohibiting RONS/pollutant interactions, thus resulting in significant reduction of the pollutant degradation efficiency [6, 14]. Nevertheless, as depicted in Fig. 5, the decrease of pollutant degradation in presence of TiO₂ and ZnO was much lower compared to air-CAP alone and the impact of soil humidity becomes much less intense. For instance, during TiO₂-plasmacatalysis, trifluralin degradation efficiency decreased from 99.9% (dry soil) to 80.8 (2 wt% soil moisture) and 80.5% (5 wt% soil moisture) leading to a degradation reduction ~19% which is much lower compared to the ~54% degradation reduction observed for 5 wt% soil moisture during the plasma process without catalyst. This could be attributed to the fact that the presence of water molecules is considered a key-factor in the formation of active species on the surface of TiO₂ and ZnO during CAP [50, 51]. The established reactions water molecules can be involved in the presence of appropriate catalysts to promote the generation of “new aqueous” active species are described in the following reactions:

Therefore, the inhibitory effect of water molecules in preventing the plasma species to travel large distances through the soil pores and reach the pollutant, is partially offset by the ability of the catalysts to generate ROS locally that have to travel shorter distances to reach the pollutant. The plasma-catalytic mechanisms resulting in improved degradation performance are discussed in detail below.

Figure 5. Effect of soil moisture on trifluralin degradation efficiency in the presence and absence of TiO₂ and ZnO after 10 min of air-plasma treatment (catalyst loading: 2 wt%).

3.5. Plasma species identification and quantification in the presence and absence of catalysts

3.5.1. OES measurements

For the identification of the main RONS we conducted OES measurements both in the absence and presence of the catalysts (TiO₂ and ZnO); a representative emission spectrum for each case is illustrated in Fig. 1d. Similar excitation peaks were observed between the various CAP systems, nevertheless they varied in their intensity. The predominant detected species include the excited nitrogen molecules (N₂, Second Positive System) from 315 to 405 nm and the excited N₂⁺ (First Negative System) from 390 to 440 nm caused by the electron-impact excitation and ionization of molecular nitrogen, respectively along with emissions for the ·OH from 297 nm to 311 nm [52, 53]. The weak emissions of O₂⁺ at 427 and 527 nm [54], ·O at 777 and 844 nm, Hγ at 434 nm and NOγ (230-280 nm) were also included [55, 56]. The addition of TiO₂ and ZnO resulted in the enhancement of the emission intensities corresponding to ROS and at the same time the decrease of emission lines corresponding to the excited N₂ molecules. Thus, an alteration of the relative concentrations between RNS/ROS is observed implying an enhancement of ROS concentrations in air-CAP/ZnO and air-CAP/TiO₂ systems compared to air-CAP alone. Therefore, ROS (e.g. ·OH) is expected to have a significant role in the plasmacatalytic system for trifluralin degradation in soil. The ROS enhancement in the presence of catalysts is further supported by the exhaust gas analysis that follows.

3.5.2. O₃ and NO_x concentration in the plasma exhaust gases

Plasmacatalytic efforts for soil remediation are still very limited whereas the understanding of mechanisms involved remains challenging. O₃ and NO_x are among the main long-lived gaseous species produced during air-CAP. In order to move a step

forward towards the understanding of the plasmacatalytic mechanism and the enhancement of the organic pollutant degradation efficiency (as already discussed in detail above), O₃ and NO_x concentrations were measured in the plasma exhaust gases in the presence and absence of TiO₂ and ZnO catalysts under both air and oxygen atmospheres.

The NO_x (NO and NO₂) and O₃ concentrations were determined in the plasma exhaust gases both for plasma alone and plasmacatalysis process (Fig. 6). NO was not detected possibly due to its rapid overoxidation to NO₂ thus NO_x concentration is effectively equal to that of NO₂. This in turn implies that NO is destroyed fast and cannot have a major role in the degradation of trifluralin. The presence of TiO₂ and ZnO resulted in a significant increase in NO₂ concentration compared to the plasma alone process (Fig. 6); evidence of higher concentration of oxidizing species in the presence of catalysts. In particular, NO₂ concentration increased from 650 ppm (air-CAP) to 880 and 1168 at 1 wt% ZnO and 1 wt% TiO₂, respectively (Fig. 6a). On the other hand, when the percentage of the catalyst was increased to 2 wt%, the impact of the two catalysts on trifluralin degradation was similar both on trifluralin degradation (Fig. 3c) and NO₂ concentration (Fig. 6b); NO₂ concentration was measured to be 1200 ppm and 1180 ppm for 2 wt% ZnO and 2 wt% TiO₂, respectively.

The concentration of O₃ in the plasma alone was higher than that in the CAP-TiO₂ and CAP-ZnO systems both under air (Fig. 6c) and oxygen (Fig. 6d) atmospheres. In addition, in all cases the O₃ concentration was gradually increased with treatment time reaching a plateau after 2 or 3 min of treatment time. For air-CAP, the final O₃ concentration was ~1300 ppm and decreased to 750 ppm and 950 ppm in the presence of TiO₂ and ZnO, respectively (Fig. 6c). Under oxygen plasma (O₂-CAP) a much higher final O₃ concentration was measured (7000 ppm) which also significantly decreased to

~4000 ppm in the presence of TiO₂ or ZnO (Fig. 6d). The attenuation of O₃ concentration under catalytic conditions could be attributed to its catalyst-induced decomposition into other species [57, 58], some of which at least, are probably actively involved in the degradation of trifluralin (also increased under both air- and O₂-CAP catalyzed conditions).

Figure 6. Concentration of the plasma-generated NO₂ in the exhaust gases during air-plasma in the absence and presence of (a) 1 wt% and (b) 2 wt% of catalyst. Concentration of the plasma-generated O₃ in the exhaust gases in the absence and presence of catalyst during (c) air-plasma and (d) O₂-plasma (catalyst loading: 2 wt%).

In particular, when plasma UV irradiates on photocatalysts, holes and electrons are generated, while the photogenerated electrons can react with O₃ and reduce it to ozone radical (O₃⁻) a highly active reactant (reaction 18) which recombines with O₃ to form O₄⁻ (reaction 19). This sequence of reactions may more than account for the decreased levels of O₃ in the presence of photocatalysts. Both O₃⁻ and O₄⁻ are short-lived species decomposing to produce O₂ (possibly in the singlet state too) and superoxide anions (O₂⁻) through the reactions (20) and (21) [59] which enhance further the degradation of trifluralin. Additionally, O₃ can be decomposed on the catalyst surface resulting in the generation of atomic oxygen (reaction 22). Furthermore, additional superoxide anions can be generated through the reaction of e_{cb}⁻ and molecular oxygen (23) and the highly reactive ·OH resulting from h_{vb}⁺ reacting with water present in the soil (reaction 24) [60]:

3.6. Proposed degradation pathways in the presence and absence of catalysts

Trifluralin is among the most common hazardous and persistent soil pollutants therefore its degradants in soil have been studied in detail [61]. Golab et al. compiled the first comprehensive catalogue of 43 trifluralin degradants and assigned a number to each one from TR2 to TR44 (TR1 being trifluralin) for future reference [62]. This

systematic designation was adopted by regulating authorities [63], other researchers in this field, including us, by reporting newly identified trifluralin degradants with a new TR number, with the count continuing from the last reported one. In our previous article on plasma-induced trifluralin degradation in soil samples, we identified several new degradants and applied the same numbering system with the count reaching TR56 [13]. In this work we tentatively identified several new trifluralin degradants generated under plasma in the presence and absence of photocatalysts such as TiO₂ and ZnO. Following the established convention describe above, these were designated TR57-69 (Fig. 7).

In general, the trifluralin degradants found are consistent with those reported previously and the process appears to be governed by the same established reactions taking place under air/O₂-CAP conditions [13]. For example, the initial degradant of trifluralin is associated with hydroxylation of the alkyl chains at the carbon atom next to the nitrogen atom (TR57, Fig. 7) and the resulting hemiaminal may be hydrolyzed leading to dealkylated derivatives (essentially all TRs). The nitro groups are reduced by electron transfers successively to nitroso, hydroxylamine (TR63) and aniline intermediates (TR59, TR60) or may be replaced by OH/OOH (TR65, TR66, TR67, TR68 and TR69; green set of degradants), or may be cleaved entirely (TR65, TR68 and TR69). Hydroxylamine intermediate from partial reduction of nitro groups may participate in oxidative cyclizations giving rise to benzoxadiazoles such as the one in TR63. Finally, hemiaminal intermediates such as TR57 may be oxidized further to produce an amide (TR59) which may intramolecularly condense with an adjacent aniline to produce 2-alkylbenzimidazoles who may in turn suffer α -hydroxylation followed by further oxidation or ketones (TR60, TR61 and TR64) or fragmentation (TR62).

An interesting observation from this study is the fate of the trifluoromethyl group (CF₃) present in trifluralin. In our previous work where we studied intermediate/late

degradants we highlighted the survival of this group in the relatively high molecular products detected except in one that was found to have been converted to a carboxylic acid. In this study where early degradants were interrogated, we found that the CF₃ group had been converted to carboxylic acid degradants in nearly half of the low molecular weight trifluralin degradants detected. This suggests that the CF₃ conversion to carboxylic acids is more favorable in the early, trifluralin-like structures (degraded further and escaping detection at longer treatment times) while it becomes more resistant in the higher heterocycles and larger molecular weight species formed as degradation proceeds. Degradant TR68 is particularly important as it constitutes a signature of mechanism by which the CF₃ group is metabolized. It appears that after partial or complete de-alkylation of trifluralin and replacement/modification of at least one of the nitro groups into a less sterically demanding moiety, the resulting aniline can conjugate its electrons into the para-position of the aromatic ring and expel a fluoride anion from the CF₃ group giving rise to a benzoquinone imine type of intermediate (TR-Q, R= H or propyl). This is not possible in the parent trifluralin as the N-substituents at the sp² hybridized nitrogen would clash with the large nitro groups. Successive hydroxyl attacks at the difluoroalkenyl carbon atom of TR-Q type of intermediates lead to the formation of carboxylic acid. The high reactivity of TR-Qs is undoubtedly responsible for escaping detection (hence grey and no number assigned in Fig. 7), yet they are the most probable and reasonable precursors to TR68 and the members of the green set of carboxylic acid degradants. It is also possible that the carboxylic acid groups found in some of the dimeric degradants, is formed in this way prior to a dimerization process (TR61 precursor to TR60) although hydrolysis of the CF₃ group post dimerization may equally happen via related quinoid intermediates. The increased degradation of CF₃ is prime importance as this group, aside from its

electron-withdrawing and lipophilic properties, is frequently installed in drug molecules and agrochemicals to impart metabolic/oxidative stability and survive long enough to exert their biological effects. On the other hand, this undermines the natural and non-natural degradation of fluorinated molecules. The present work supports an important development in degrading efficiently metabolically resistant fluorinated molecules such as PFAS, that constitute a challenge in modern remediation technologies.

In terms of similarities and differences among the CAP/TiO₂, CAP/ZnO and CAP alone processes it appears that the TR-Q pathway (green set of degradants, Fig. 7) is favored the most under all conditions and the degradants resulting from this pathway are the most abundant. Nevertheless, the CAP alone process and that containing ZnO (CAP/ZnO) are more similar to one another whereas the CAP/TiO₂ process differs slightly in terms of preferred degradation pathways. Finally, the catalysts besides their limited contact with the solid pollutant, it is possible that they participate in a photocatalytic reaction pathway that involves electron transfers to and from the pollutant generating pollutant species with increased reactivity.

Figure 7. Possible intermediate degradants and plasma-catalytic pathways involved in the plasma-induced degradation of trifluralin in soil with and without catalysts. The ratios indicated reflect the relative intensities of ionization in MS of the same set of species under the three different conditions (plasma gas: air, catalyst loading: 2 wt%).

Conclusively, based on the findings already presented herein related to (i) catalysts characterization after plasma treatment, (ii) differences in the concentration of RONS between plasma alone and plasma-catalysis, (iii) enhancement of pollutant degradation efficiency/rate/energy efficiency in the presence of TiO₂/ZnO catalysts under the various conditions (catalyst nature/loading, plasma gas, soil humidity, etc.) and (iv) plasma-induced intermediates of pollutant degradation in the presence and absence of catalysts, a possible plasma-catalytic mechanism for the degradation of organic pollutants in soil is presented in Fig. 8.

Figure 8. A schematic representation of possible plasma-catalytic processes related to pollutant degradation.

4. Conclusions

A plasma reactor capable of producing micro-discharges directly into the interconnected soil channels was combined with TiO₂ and ZnO catalysts resulting in complete and high energy-efficient degradation of trifluralin with a maximum energy efficiency ~22 mg/kJ which is one of the highest ever reported. The presence of both catalysts enhanced substantially the pollutant degradation efficiency/rate and the energy efficiency of the process (3-fold increase). The order in pollutant degradation kinetics was O₂-plasma/TiO₂ > O₂-plasma/ZnO > air-plasma/TiO₂ > air-plasma/ZnO > O₂-plasma ≈ air-plasma. The previously known inhibitory effect of the soil humidity on pollutant degradation was less intense in the presence of catalysts; i.e. the reduction in trifluralin degradation was ~19% in the presence of TiO₂, much lower than the ~54% reduction during the plasma-alone process. The detection/measurement of plasma species in the gas phase and the reactor exhaust gases showed that in the presence of

TiO₂ and ZnO a significant increase in NO₂ concentration and a noticeable reduction of O₃ with the latter being converted to more active ROS. For both catalysts, O₂-plasma revealed a better performance compared to air-plasma, indicating an additional O₃ decomposition and ROS enhancement when O₂ was used as the plasma carrier gas. The degradation pathways were elucidated revealing similar processes between plasma-alone and plasma-catalysis. Furthermore, a significant number of trifluralin degradants detected in this study have the parent trifluoromethyl group converted to carboxylic acid. This increased degradation of fluorinated groups is particularly encouraging and holds promise in developing our process further to encompass degradation of polyfluorinated pollutants such as PFAS. Overall, this study provides useful insights on the plasma-catalytic mechanisms towards a highly-efficient and sustainable soil remediation approach.

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